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Exploring the Intersectionality of Employment Opportunities for Immigrant Woman in Canada: A Socio-Economic Analysis

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Abstract

Introduction: Canada has the multicultural landscape which consists of diverse population. This research delves multifaceted dynamics on the intersectionality of employment opportunities for woman in Canada. Immigrant woman has encountered several barriers on accessing the meaningful employment opportunities. They faced socio-economic disparities, inequality of the experience factors and cultural factors.

Objectives: It focuses on analyzing the influences of employment opportunities for immigrant woman in Canada as a dependent variable with socio-economic status, experience and cultural background as an independent variable. It also provides a clear overview on how immigrant woman with color faced the challenges and identify the key areas for its improvement.

Design: This study adopts quantitative research design for the data collection. It surveys with the focus group of immigrant woman i.e. woman with color. This research collects the data to understand the perspective and real life experience of immigrant woman with color across the socio-economic status, experience and cultural backgrounds.

Findings: The finding of the study highlights the relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women with color in Canada with socio-economic status, experience level and cultural background. Socio-economic status includes the factors income and resources. Experience plays the vital role on the recognition through skill and higher paying employment opportunities. Cultural backgrounds include the social networking which has influences on employment outcomes. It shows the significant response on socio-economic status and cultural background but non-significant response on experience level.

Practical Implications: With the clear glance on intersecting the influences of socio-economic status, experience level and cultural background; future researcher can develop a targeted policies and programs which can enhance and contribute to Canada's social and economic prosperity.

Originality/Value: This research paper is the original research work carried out through the self-study from the questionnaire distribution to immigrant woman with color. Primary data is collected to examine the socio-economic status, experience and cultural background of immigrant women with color.

Keywords: Employment Opportunities, Immigrant Woman with Color, Intersectionality, Socio-economic Status, Experience, Cultural Background

Introduction

Intersecting identities and diverse socio-economic dynamics has created the intersectionality of employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada. Canada is recognized as the country having one of the largest economy supported by the diverse workforce who enter as an immigrant in nation (Kalyanaraman, 2022). It has paved the way for empowering immigrant women through meaningful contribution in various sectors of economy. Due to constant increment in number of immigrants, Canada have the tapestry of challenges to settle professional work force in their respective job (Bhuyan, Osazuwa, Schmidt, Kwon, Rundle, & Park, 2024). By delving the nuances of gender, this challenge further escalated as highlighted by various researches. With waves of immigrants setting foot in Canada for better opportunities, immigrant women often had found themselves at the margin of labor market (Murage & Smith, 2023). Despite being the country strides towards the gender equality, immigrant women's accessibility for quality work in labor market is still at a low level (Hamilton, Easley, & Dixon, 2018). Intersectionality of employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada not only limits itself to gender issue but also addresses the issues related to color, race, ethnicity, language and nationality (Houle, 2020). It reveals the naïve struggles of immigrant women who arrive in Canada from diverse backgrounds (Sodia, 2019). Another crucial factor that exclude immigrant women to get quality job is socio-economic factors such as lack of work experience, recognition barrier, language proficiency and so on (Okeke-Ihejirika, Punjani, & Salami, 2022). Furthermore, lack of robust social networking also plays significant role in deterring immigrant women from accessing quality employment opportunities (Wall & Wood, 2023). Hence, Canada can exemplify the principles of equity and inclusiveness to enhance the contributions of immigrant women in multiple sectors, thereby enhancing the nation's socio-economic fabric.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study on the title "**Exploring the Intersectionality of Employment Opportunities for Immigrant Woman in Canada: A Socio-economic Analysis**" is as follows:

- To analyze the employment opportunities for immigrant woman with color in Canada.
- To evaluate socio-economic status of immigrant woman with color in Canada.
- To assess experience level of immigrant woman with color in Canada.
- To find out the cultural background of immigrant woman with color in Canada.

Hypothesis of the Study

The hypothesis of the study on the title "**Exploring the Intersectionality of Employment Opportunities for Immigrant Woman in Canada: A Socio-economic Analysis**" are as follows:

H₁: There is significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant woman with color in Canada and socio-economic status.

H₂: There is significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant woman with color in Canada and experience level.

H₃: There is significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant woman with color in Canada and cultural background.

Literature Review

Array of prior literature work defines the multifaceted nature of employment opportunities for immigrant women with color in Canada. Some of the key challenging factors of getting employment opportunities for immigrant women with color in Canada are structural barriers, socio-economic status, lack of Canadian work experience and diversity of culture (MacDonnell, Dastjerdi, Bokore, & Tharao, 2024). Moving forward with a holistic approach, although Canada has strict laws and policies against color discrimination, inclusiveness in the

workplace or equal opportunities for immigrant women with color has remained limited within the mere core written laws and word of mouth until now (Mensah, 2014). However, there have been multiple attempts for addressing the concern from different arenas, which has been identified in this paper and enlisted as dependent and independent variables.

Employment Opportunities for Immigrant Woman with color in Canada

Employment opportunities for immigrant women with color in Canada persists multi-diverse environment. Canadian labor market has been profoundly influenced by legacy of racism and sexism in past (Nichols, 2018). History reveals the injustice of employment disparities for immigrant women with color in the labor market (Crawford, Kapisavanhu, Moore, Crawford, & Lundy, 2023). The immigrant women with color come with unique talent and skill. Yet, various studies have revealed the significantly low wages for their work in many sectors of Canada (Yu, 2021). Credential recognition barriers and discriminatory recruitment practices also provoke for non-native women with color in Canada (Morgenshtern, 2019). With collaboration between government agencies and community organizations, a ray of hope has emerged for equitable employment opportunities for immigrant women with color in Canada (Hande, Akram, & Condratto, 2019). However, this effort is just a tips of iceberg in creating an equitable environment for foreign women settler with color.

Socio-Economic Status

This research papers after prior analysis of past research work has addressed socio-economic status as one of the independent variables. Scholars argue that demographic factors such as socio-economic factors also play pivotal role in employment opportunities for alien women with color in Canada (Anucha, 2019). Both federal and provincial level of Canada have been implementing the strict policy for mitigating employment disparities among immigrant women of diverse ethnicities (Mutune, 2022). Contemporary research of early 2020s has revealed the failure to adequately address the issue on recruitment sector (Shields & Lujan, 2021). Research has also shown that immigrant women from lower socio-economic background often face huddles on finding quality employment opportunity in developed country (Matias, Silva, & Farago, 2020). In post-Covid era, women with color from immigrant communities are more vulnerable and are exploited in work place as they often lack on social capital and access to quality education (Olson, Naevestad, Orru, Schiefflers, & Meyer, 2023). On contrary, those with higher socio-economic status are easily accepted in labor market due to their grater networks (Gingrich, 2010). Hence, socio-economic status plays significant role for getting quality employment opportunity in Canada.

Experience level

There is vital role of experience level for shaping the employment opportunities for immigrant women with color in Canada which requires nuanced exploration. Research underscores the significance of experience level in mitigating structural inequalities prevailing in Canadian labor market to foster equity for immigrant women with color (Caidi, Muzaffar, & Kalbfleisch, 2024). The immigrant women who have fair skin with higher experience level are more likely to get quality employment opportunities in Canadian labor market as compared to immigrant women who have different complexion having quality work experience (Machado, Cruz, & Falcao, 2023). This clearly resembles the unfair practices prevailing in labor market for immigrant women with color. Studies have also shown that immigrant women with color in Canada with higher educational qualification often face difficulty securing employment comparability (Zou, et al., 2023). Generally, newcomer woman with color having experience brings prevalence of credentials and professional segmentation within Canadian labor market (Islam, 2022). Hence, by fostering the equitable employment practices, Canada in future can really harness the potential of immigrant women with color that can help promote the economic prosperity.

Cultural Background

Canada is the country with multiple social identity and cultural diversity providing lots of opportunities for immigrant women (Motia, 2023). Canadian labor market provides both opportunities and challenges for immigrant women (Vujinovic, 2017). With cultural diversity, immigrant women found array of employment prospect in one hand while deep rooted barriers of racism and sexism often obstruct them from getting quality job opportunities (Moffitt, Nardon, & Zhang, 2019). Immigrant women with color found difficulty in accessing quality employment opportunities due to discriminatory recruitment practices and lack of cultural competence in Canada (Umaigba, 2023). Despite having higher educational degrees and quality work experience in home countries, immigrant women with color are often unable to navigate in Canadian job market due to cultural and language differences (Lightman, Banerjee, Tungohan, Leon, & Kelly, 2021). Thus, cultural background plays pivot role for accessing meaningful employment opportunities in Canada.

Figure no.1 Research Framework of the Study

Source: Wilkes & Wu (2019) Immigration, Discrimination, and Trust: A Simply Complex Relationship. *Frointer of Sociology*, 4. doi:10.3389/fsoc.2019.00032

Research Methodology

Research employs in-depth exploration of socio-economic aspect to explore the intersectionality of employment opportunities for immigrant women with color in Canada. Researcher incorporates quantitative approach to provide comprehensive information about the factor influencing Canadian labor market for immigrant women with color. The research has collected primary data from immigrant women with color residing in Canada. A convenient sampling technique is adopted and 200 participants are selected for research strictly ensuring ethical consideration. A self-structured questionnaire is designed and obtained data are statistically analyzed. Through rigorous research methodology, research has made significant contribution in-depth analysis of the challenges prevailing in Canadian labor market for immigrant women with color that can facilitate the promotion of inclusiveness practices as envisioned by Constitution of Canada.

Data Analysis

One-way ANOVA analysis is conducted to explore the disparities in between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with demographic characteristics. Multiple regression analysis proves the hypothetical relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with independent variable i.e. socio-economic status, experience level and cultural background with the help of IBM SPSS software.

One Way ANOVA Analysis

The ANOVA test of dependent variable employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada and the demographic variable is analyzed. The significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada and demographic variable are shown in the following table:

Table 1 One way ANOVA test between Employee Opportunities for Immigrant Women in Canada with Age

ANOVA					
Employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	790.219	6	131.703	4.568	.000
Within Groups	5565.061	193	28.835		
Total	6355.280	199			

It shows that the One Way ANOVA test is analyzed between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with age. The F-value= 4.568, p-value is .000 which is less than .50. That means there is significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with age.

Table 2 One way ANOVA test between Employee Opportunities for Immigrant Women in Canada with Marital Status

ANOVA					
Employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	18.619	3	6.206	.192	.902
Within Groups	6336.661	196	32.330		
Total	6355.280	199			

It shows that the One Way ANOVA test is analyzed between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with marital status. The F-value= .192, p-value is .902 which is more than .50. That means there is no significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with marital status.

Table 3 One way ANOVA test between Employee Opportunities for Immigrant Women in Canada with Academic Qualification

ANOVA					
Employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	999.626	5	199.925	7.242	.000
Within Groups	5355.654	194	27.606		
Total	6355.280	199			

It shows that the One Way ANOVA test is analyzed between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with academic qualification. The F-value= 7.242, p-value is .000 which is less than .50. That means there is significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with academic qualification.

Table 4 One way ANOVA test between Employee Opportunities for Immigrant Women in Canada with Occupation

ANOVA					
Employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Group	63.601	1	63.601	2.002	.159
Within Groups	6291.679	198	31.776		
Total	6355.280	199			

It shows that the One Way ANOVA test is analyzed between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with occupation. The F-value= 2.002, p-value is .159 which is less than .50. That means there is significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with occupation.

Table 5 One way ANOVA test between Employee Opportunities for Immigrant Women in Canada with Job Experience

ANOVA					
Employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	411.771	5	82.354	2.688	.023
Within Groups	5943.509	194	30.637		
Total	6355.280	199			

It shows that the One Way ANOVA test is analyzed between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with job experience. The F-value= 2.688, p-value is .023 which is less than .50. That means there is significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with job experience.

Table 6 One way ANOVA test between Employee Opportunities for Immigrant Women in Canada with Sexual Orientation

ANOVA					
Employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	80.571	5	16.114	.498	.777
Within Groups	6274.709	194	32.344		
Total	6355.280	199			

It shows that the One Way ANOVA test is analyzed between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with sexual orientation. The F-value= .498, p-value is .777 which is more than .50. That means there is no significant relationship between employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with sexual orientation.

Multiple Regression Analysis

It is the statistical method which is used to examine the hypothetical relationship between the dependent variable i.e. employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with independent variable i.e. socio-economic status, experience level and cultural background. It studies about how the independent variable influence on the employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada focusing to woman with color in Canada.

Table 7 Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Coefficients ^a		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	7.360	1.399		5.260	.000
Socio-economic status	.540	.073	.623	7.447	.000
Experience Level	.039	.090	.037	.434	.665
Cultural Background	.138	.067	.139	2.072	.040

a. Dependent Variable: Employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada

Interpretation of Multiple Regressions

Socio-Economic Status

The coefficient value for socio-economic status is .540 and the significant value is .000 which is statistically significant with the p-value less than .50. This indicates there is significant relationship between socio-economic status and employee opportunities for immigrant women in Canada. Thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Experience Level

The coefficient value for experience level is .039 and the significant value is .665 which is statistically significant with the p-value more than .50. This indicates there is no significant relationship between experience level and employee opportunities for immigrant women in Canada. Thus, hypothesis 2 is rejected.

Cultural Background

The coefficient value for cultural background is .138 and the significant value is .040 which is statistically significant with the p-value less than .50. This indicates there is significant relationship between cultural background and employee opportunities for immigrant women in Canada. Thus, hypothesis 3 is accepted.

Conclusion

This study has the greater positive response regarding the socio-economic status and cultural background in determining employment opportunities for immigrant women in Canada with reference to woman with color. The experience level addresses the barriers and does not plays the important roles in shaping the employment opportunity to woman with color. Networking opportunities through career counseling can be applied to bridge the gap in employment opportunities.

Practical Implication

Policy makers in Canada must focuses on improving the socio-economic condition for immigrant woman with color which provides the resources for skill development. As the result shows the lesser impact of experience level in this research, it will be more beneficial in focusing more to facilitate the better recognition to foreign credentials. Many more efforts can be made to recognize and validate the foreign work experience.

References

- Anucha, U. (2019). Negotiated Challenges in the Workplace: Immigrant Women's Views and Experiences of Employment in Canada. *Journal of Women and Social Work* , 27 (4), 420-434.
- Bhuyan, R., Osazuwa, S., Schmidt, C., Kwon, I., Rundle, A., & Park, Y. (2024). Canadian Social Workers' Attitudes Toward Immigrants with Different Legal Statuses in Canada. *Journal of Social Work* .
- Caidi, N., Muzaffar, S., & Kalbfleisch, E. (2024). Contested Imaginaries: Workfinding Information Practices of STEM-Trained Immigrant Women in Canada. *Journal of Documentation* .
- Crawford, J., Kapisavanhu, N., Moore, J., Crawford, C., & Lundy, T. (2023). A Critical Review of Social Exclusion and Inclusion among Immigrant and Refugee Women. *Hindawi* , 1, 1-20.
- Gingrich, L. G. (2010). The Symbolic Economy of Trans-order Governance: A Case Study of Subjective Exclusion and Migrant Women from Mexico. *Refugee Survey Quarterly* , 161-184.
- Hamilton, T. G., Easley, J. A., & Dixon, A. R. (2018). Black Immigration, Occupational Niches, and Earnings Disparities Between U.S.-Born and Foreign-Born Blacks in the United States. *The Russell Sage Foundation Journal of the Social Sciences* , 4 (1), 60-77.
- Hande, M. J., Akram, A. M., & Condratto, S. (2019). "All of This Happens Here?": Diminishing Perceptions of Canada through Immigrants' Precarious Work in Ontario. *Journal of International Migration and Integration* , 21 (2).
- Houle, R. (2020). *Changes in the Socioeconomic Situation of Canada's Black Population, 2001 to 2016*. Statistics Canada – Catalogue no. 89-657-X2020001.
- Islam, M. K. (2022). Income Attainment of Immigrant Women in Canada: Does Region of Birth Matter? *Khulna University Studies* , 10 (1&2), 263-272.
- Kalyanaraman, S. (2022). Integrated or segregated in Ontario: Exploring 'South Asians' Settlers' Heterogeneity in the Context of Specific Immigrant Urban Spatialities. *GLRC Working Paper* , 1-12.
- Lightman, N., Banerjee, R., Tungohan, E., Leon, C. d., & Kelly, P. (2021). An Intersectional Pathway Penalty: Filipina Immigrant Women Inside and Outside Canada's Live-In Caregiver Program. *International Migration* , 60 (2), 29-48.
- MacDonnell, J. A., Dastjerdi, F. M., Bokore, N., & Tharao, W. (2024). Activism and Immigrant Women's Mental Health and Wellbeing: Building Canadian Service Provider Capacity in the Settlement and Mental Health Sectors. *Health Care for Women International* , 45 (5), 579-599.
- Machado, M. M., Cruz, E., & Falcao, R. (2023). Immigrant Entrepreneurship of Brazilian Women in Toronto, Canada. *Internext* , 18 (2), 113-129.
- Matias, G. P., Silva, G. R., & Farago, F. E. (2020). Precarization of Work and Migration: A Review of the International Literature. *Review of International Business* , 15 (1), 19-36.
- Mensah, J. (2014). Black Continental African Identities in Canada: Exploring the Intersections of Identity Formation and Immigrant Transnationalism. *Journal of Canadian studies* , 48 (3), 5-29.
- Moffitt, U., Nardon, L., & Zhang, H. (2019). Becoming Canadian: Immigrant Narratives of Professional Attainment. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations* , 78 (3).

- Morgenshtern, M. (2019). "My Family's Weight on My Shoulders": Experiences of Jewish Immigrant Women from the Former Soviet Union (FSU) in Toronto. *Social Sciences* , 8 (86), 1-23.
- Motia, M. (2023). Connecting Artfully Toward Promoting the Mental Health of Immigrant Women in Canada: A Literature Review. . *Canadian Social Work Review* , 40 (2), 157-177.
- Murage, A., & Smith, J. (2023). Multifaceted Precarity: Pandemic Experiences of Recent Immigrant Women in the Accommodation and Food Services Sector. *BMC Public Health* , 23.
- Mutune, C. N. (2022). *Amplifying the Voices of Kenyan Women in Canada: The Implicit Contradiction of the Federal Skilled Worker Program*. Toronto: York University.
- Nichols, L. (2018). Newcomer Women's Experience of Immigration and Precarious Work in Toronto. *Critical Studies An International and Interdisciplinary Journal* , 14 (1), 7-30.
- Okeke-Ihejirika, P., Punjani, N. S., & Salami, B. (2022). African Immigrant's Women Experiences on Extended Family Relations. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* , 19 (14).
- Olson, A., Naevestad, T.-O., Orru, K. N., Schieffeler, A., & Meyer, S. F. (2023). The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Socially Marginalised Women: Material and Mental Health Outcomes. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* , 93.
- Shields, J., & Lujan, O. (2021). *Immigrant Youth in Canada: A Literature Review of Migrant Youth Settlement and Service Issues*. Toronto: York University.
- Sodia, J. K. (2019). *Silence as Protection: Construction and Deconstruction of Violent Subjects in Media Portrayals of South-Asian and White Incidents of Domestic Violence*. York University.
- Umaigba, K. (2023). A Critical Literature Review of the Impact of Precarious Work on the Mental Health of Immigrant Women in Canada: A Qualitative Exploration. . *Canadian Journal of Nursing Research* , 55 (3), 305-318.
- Vujinovic, S. (2017). *How Do Three Immigrant Women from Former Yugoslavia Perceive the Role of Accent in Intelligibility and Comprehensibility in the Canadian Workplace?* North York, Ontario: York University.
- Wall, K., & Wood, S. (2023). *Education and Earnings of Canadian-Born Black Populations*. Insights on Canadian Society.
- Wilkes, R., & Wu, C. (2019). Immigration, Discrimination, and Trust: A Simply Complex Relationship. *Frontier of Sociology* , 4.
- Yu, X. (2021). Bourdieu's Talk: High-Education-Low-Income Issue Among Skilled Immigrants from Chinese Mainland in Canada. *Chinese Political Science Review* , 7 (2), 1-17.
- Zou, P., Alam, A., Shao, J., Luo, Y., Huang, Y., Zhang, H., et al. (2023). Midlife Transition Experiences of South Asian Immigrant Women in Canada: A Qualitative Exploration. *Canadian Journal of Nursing Research* , 55 (11).